

The species of the genus *Belgrandia* (Caenogastropoda, Hydrobiidae) in the Iberian Peninsula

Las especies del género *Belgrandia* (Caenogastropoda, Hydrobiidae) en la Península Ibérica

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ABSTRACT

The species of the genus *Belgrandia* Bourguignat, 1869 from the Iberian Peninsula are discussed. Four taxa were previously known, but some of them were considered as having subspecific level. A new species from Portugal is described: *B. silviae* spec. nov. Conchological, anatomical and radulae data are provided for all the species involved. The known geographic distribution area is given, reporting new localities for some of the species.

RESUMEN

Se discuten las especies pertenecientes al género *Belgrandia* Bourguignat, 1869 de la Península Ibérica. Cuatro taxones eran previamente conocidas, aunque alguno considerado en un nivel subespecífico. Se describe una nueva especie de Portugal: *B. silviae* spec. nov. Se muestran los caracteres de la concha y morfología de las partes blandas y de las radulas de todas las especies incluidas. Se presenta la distribución conocida, aportando nuevas localidades para algunas de ellas.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Belgrandia* Bourguignat, 1869 (Caenogastropoda, Hydrobiidae) is present in European springs and streams, in Dalmatia, southern France, Italy, Spain and Portugal, according to KABAT AND HERSHLER (1993). In their work the evolution of this genus, as well as its relationships and synonyms are commented upon. Some species from Portugal were described by French and German authors (PALADILHE, 1867; CLESSIN, 1878; BOETTGER, 1963). NOBRE (1930) did not admit the validity of these taxa and considered that all represent only forms of *B. gibba* (Draparnaud, 1805). This species lives in southern France (KABAT AND HERSHLER (1993) and it is improbable

that populations of the same species are found as far away as Portugal, as admitted by BOETERS (1988). ROLÁN (1999) mentioned *B. lusitanica* (Paladilhe, 1867) informing that it is a species in risk of extinction due to the small area where it lives. HAASE (2000) published a revision on this genus in Europe including the species in the Iberian Peninsula.

Recently, new samplings collected by the junior author allowed us to get a better idea of the distribution area. The study of all this new material allowed us to compare populations collected in several localities in Portugal. Other samples had been collected by the senior author years ago.

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As far as we know, only one species is present in Eastern Spain, with few populations dispersed along a wide distribution range between Cataluña and Comunidad Valenciana. The situation in Portugal is quite the reverse, the genus exhibiting a significant radiation. In an area of only 90x50 km, four species are present, one of which, *B. silviae* spec. nov., is here described as new to science. This territory corresponds to the northern half of the Lusitanian Basin, in central western Portugal, which in the Upper Pliocene was still submerged.

Abbreviations:

MNCN Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid

MHNG Museum d'Histoire Naturelle, Geneve
MHNS Museo de Historia Natural de la Universidad de Santiago de Compostela (collection of Emilio Rolán)
MNHN Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris
BMNH The Natural History Museum, London
MHNP Museu Nacional de História Natural, Faculdade de Ciências do Porto (former Museu de Zoologia Augusto Nobre)
SMF Naturmuseum und Forschungsanstalt Senckenberg, Frankfurt
CAO Collection of Álvaro de Oliveira
CHB Collection of Hans Boeters
sp live specimen
s empty shell

TAXONOMIC PART

Family HYDROBIIDAE Troschel, 1857
Genus *Belgrandia* Bourguignat, 1869

Type species: *Cyclostoma gibbum* Draparnaud, 1805.

Belgrandia lusitanica (Paladilhe, 1867) (Figs. 1-12, 69)

Hydrobia lusitanica Paladilhe, 1867. *Rev. Mag. Zool. Pure appl.* (2); 19: 92, pl. 21, figs. 1-4. [Type locality: Fonte das Lágrimas, after Coimbra, Portugal].

Belgrandia occidentalis Clessin, 1878. *Malakozool.* Bl., 25: 120, lám. 4, fig. 7-9. [Type locality: Coimbra, Portugal].

Belgrandia gibba Draparnaud, 1805. In NOBRE (1930: 205, fig. 36).

Type material: Lectotype designated and figured by HAASE (2000: fig. 3 E) in MHNG.

Type locality: Fonte das Lágrimas,

Other material studied: About 150 sp, leg. E. Rolán, (9-March-1989; 30-June-1990); 132 sp, leg. A. de Oliveira (5-January-2008). All from Fonte das Lágrimas, Quinta das Lágrimas, (NE4849), Coimbra, province of Beira Litoral, Portugal.

Description: Shell (Figs. 1-8) oval-cylindrical, somewhat elongated, whorls convex, with deep suture.

Protoconch (Fig. 9) with about 1 whorl, the separation from the teleoconch being very difficult to see; diameter: nucleus about 90 µm; first ½ whorl, about 240 µm. Microsculpture (Fig. 10) with minute depressions, which with high magnification (Fig. 11) are seen as having geometrical shape and separa-

tion wall elevated and with numerous lines.

Teleoconch with about three whorls, with some irregular spiral lines and prosocline growth lines.

Aperture slightly ovoid, continuous and with a fine peristoma, a little undulating. Externally, a little before the end of the spire, there is an axially elongated thickening, very constant, only absent from juveniles.

Figures 1-10. *Belgrandia lusitanica* (Paladilhe, 1867). 1-8: shells, 1,6, 1,7, 1,5, 1,4, 1,6, 1,4, 1,5, 1,8 mm, Fonte das Lágrimas, Coimbra; 9: protoconch; 10: detail of the microsculpture.

Figuras 1-10. Belgrandia lusitanica (Paladilhe, 1867). 1-8: conchas, 1,6; 1,7; 1,5; 1,4; 1,6; 1,4; 1,5 y 1,8 mm, Fonte das Lágrimas, Coimbra; 9: protoconcha; 10: detalle de la microescultura.

Figures 11, 12. *Belgrandia lusitanica* (Paladilhe, 1867). 11: microsculpture of the protoconch; 12: radula.

Figuras 11, 12. Belgrandia lusitanica (Paladilhe, 1867). 11: microescultura de la protoconcha; 12: rádula.

Dimensions between 1.4 and 1.9 mm in height.

Animal (also described by NOBRE, 1930) dark, with tentacles dark with a white line in the middle; the dorsum of the head is dark, only light on spaces around the eyes and the anterior part of the snout; behind the eyes there is a triangular space with cream or cream-yellowish colour; the penis (Fig. 69) is elongated, sharp-pointed, with an angle near its base, a little black on its anterior part, with a small appendix on its left side. The sole of the foot is white.

The radula (Fig. 12) is typical of hydrobids, having a central tooth with about 10 cusps, the central one more prominent; lateral teeth similar, about ten cusps; the marginal ones are different, one with near 30 small and elongated cusps, and the other spoon like with only few cusps.

Habitat: Under decaying leaves and among moss, always in shady areas with running water. This species coexists with 4 other freshwater gastropods: *Theodoxus* cf. *fluviatilis* (LINNAEUS, 1758), *Potamopyrgus antipodarum* (GRAY J. E., 1843), *Mercuria tachoensis* (FRAUENFELD,

1865) and *Physella acuta* (DRAPARNAUD, 1805).

Distribution: Known from the type locality only (Fig. 78).

Remarks: The species has been mentioned by NOBRE (1930, as *B. gibba*), and the figure of NOBRE (1930, fig. 36) is characteristic of the specimens from Quinta das Lágrimas. Also represented in BOETERS (1988) and commented by ROLÁN (1990) who described the soft parts and represented the shell, with their characteristics and typical deposits of calcium carbonatum.

Hydrobia lusitanica Paladilhe, 1867 is clearly defined by the material studied from the type locality. The name *Belgrandia gibba* Draparnaud, 1805, which NOBRE (1930) considered to be the valid one for all the Portuguese species, concerns a species only present in Corsica and the South of France, probably referred erroneously for the northwest of Italy by COSSIGNANI ET AL. (1995), and so, improbably related with the Portuguese species.

Belgrandia lusitanica had been recorded by ROLÁN (1990) considering it in high risk of extinction. At present it is satisfactory

Figures 13-22 *Belgrandia silviae* spec. nov. 13: holotype, 2.0 mm (MNCN); 14-19: Paratypes, 1.9, 2.0, 1.7, 1.8, 1.8 and 1.9 mm (MNCN); 20: detail of the aperture in the holotype; 21: protoconch; 22: microsculpture of the protoconch.

Figuras 13-22 Belgrandia silviae spec. nov. 13: holotipo, 2,0 mm (MNCN); 14-19: Paratipos, 1,9; 2,0; 1,7; 1,8; 1,8 y 1,9 mm (MNCN); 20: detalle de la abertura en el holotipo; 21: protoconcha; 22: microescultura de la protoconcha.

to known that the species is still living. But it is very important to take action to protect the future of the species.

The taxon *Belgrandia occidentalis* Clessin, 1878 is also mentioned for Coimbra, and for this reason it surely

applies to the same species and must be considered as a junior synonym. According to DANCE (1986) the Clessin collection in the Stuttgart Museum was totally destroyed in the Second World War.

Belgrandia silvoiae spec. nov. (Figs. 13-25, 70-73)

Belgrandia gibba Draparnaud, 1805. In NOBRE (1930: 206 [partim]).

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 13) plus 5 dry and 70 wet paratypes in MNCN (15.05/47571). Other paratypes in BMNH (10 sp), MHNS (80 sp), MHNP (50 sp), MNHN (10 sp), CHB (50 sp), CAO (160 sp), all live collected from the type locality, leg. A. de Oliveira, 12-February-2008 and 7-June-2008.

Type locality: In the spring of Alcabideque (NE4539), a small village 3 km east of Condeixa-a-Nova, 10 km to the south of Coimbra (and of Quinta das Lágrimas, type locality of *B. lusitanica*), province of Beira Litoral, Portugal. This spring is historically related to the old Roman town of Conímbriga, about 2 km to the west; the Romans built an aqueduct in order to carry the water into town. Later the Suevan people destroyed it. Presently, the water of this spring is carried to Ribeira de Bruscos and down the stream to the Ega River, a tributary of the Mondego River on its left margin.

Etymology: The specific name is dedicated to Sílvia Castelo, the junior author's wife, for the companionship and constant help in the field.

Description: Shell (Figs. 13-19) oval-cylindrical, somewhat elongated, whorls very convex, with a deep suture.

Protoconch (Fig. 21) with about 1 whorl or a little more, the separation with the teleoconch being very difficult to see; diameter: nucleus about 130 µm; first ½ whorl, about 260 µm. Microsculpture (Fig. 22) with a rough surface with minute depressions and numerous irregular lines.

Teleoconch with a little more than three whorls, which are very convex and show on their lower part an angulation which, on the last whorl, changes into a wide not very prominent spiral cord. The microsculpture (Fig. 23) is made of curved growth lines prosocline in the subsutural area and orthocline on the lower part.

Aperture almost circular, very irregular, continuous and undulating fine peristoma (Fig. 20). Externally, a little before the end of the spire, there is a prominent elevation which is placed on the spiral cord, not elongated axially and which forms in the inner part of the aperture an important depression. It is not present in juveniles.

Dimensions between 1.7 and 2.1 mm in height. The holotype is 2.0 mm high.

Animal dark, with tentacles dark with a white line in the middle; the dorsum of the head is dark with only white circular spaces around the eyes, which are black; the dark colour extends to the anterior part of the snout, which is white; behind the eyes there is a triangular space with cream or cream-yellowish colour; the sole of the foot is white. The penis (Figs. 70-73) is wide, sharp, with a narrow base, and one or two undulations on its internal border; a black longitudinal line is visible near the external border.

The radula (Figs. 24, 25) is typical of hydrobids, similar to the previous one but with less prominent lateral cusps in the rachidian tooth and also in the internal border of the lateral teeth.

Habitat: Under stones (limestone) lying on a coarse sandy bottom; always on surfaces devoid of all (macro) vegetation.

Distribution: Known from the type locality only (Fig. 78).

Remarks: The species had been mentioned by NOBRE (1930: 206) as *B. gibba* (Draparnaud).

Figures 23-25. *Belgrandia silviae* spec. nov. 23: microsculpture of the teleoconch; 24, 25: radula; detalle de la rádula.

Figuras 23-25. Belgrandia silviae spec. nov. 23: microescultura de la teleoconcha; 24, 25: rádula; detalle de la rádula.

Its collecting was a surprise, being so close to the type locality of *Belgrandia lusitanica*. The prominence on the external part of the last whorl which is corresponded by a wide excavation within the aperture suggested to us that the species could employ it to retain an egg as other species of Hydrobids (for

example, *Arganiella tartessae* Arconada and Ramos, 2007 and *Tarraconia rolani* Ramos, Arconada and Moreno, 2000 do this in the umbilicus). Anyway, it could be a similar strategy to that found in the family Coralliophilidae Chenu, 1859, in which the female has a similar place in the aperture to retain a capsule with

Figures 26-38. *Belgrandia heussi* C.R. Boettger, 1963. 26-30: shells, 1.9, 1.8, 1.7, 1.7 and 1.9 mm, from Alcobertas; 31-33: shells, 1.8, 1.7 and 1.7 mm, from Alviela; 34-36: shells, 1.6, 1.5 and 1.7 mm, from Lis; 37: shell, 1.9 mm, from Anços, 38: microsculpture of the teleoconch, shell from Alcobertas.

Figuras 26-38. Belgrandia heussi C.R. Boettger, 1963. 26-30: conchas, 1,9; 1,8; 1,7; 1,7 y 1,9 mm, de Alcobertas; 31-33: conchas, 1,8; 1,7 y 1,7 mm, de Alviela; 34-36: conchas, 1,6; 1,5 y 1,7 mm, de Lis; 37: concha, 1,9 mm, de Anços, 38: microescultura de la teleoconcha, concha de Alcobertas.

Figures 39-44. *Belgrandia heussi* C.R. Boettger, 1963. 39, 40: Protoconch and microsculpture, shell from Alcobertas; 41, 42: Protoconch and microsculpture, shell from Alviela; 43: Protoconch, shell from Lis. 44: Protoconch, shell from Anços.

Figuras 39-44. Belgrandia heussi C.R. Boettger, 1963. 39, 40: Protoconcha y microescultura, concha de Alcobertas; 41, 42: Protoconcha y microescultura, concha de Alviela; 43: Protoconcha, concha de Lis. 44: Protoconcha, concha de Anços.

eggs. But further collecting trying to make an immediate examination in order to confirm this point did not show any egg in this place. So we do not know the function of this prominence-excavation. When the animal is retracted, the operculum is placed deeper than this excavation.

Belgrandia lusitanica (Paladilhe, 1867) is geographically the closest species, but the morphological differences are very evident, being smaller in size, the

prominence of the last whorl is smaller, axially disposed, without a corresponding internal excavation near the aperture, the protoconch is slightly smaller, the penis has a more evident small appendix.

Like *Belgrandia lusitanica* and *B. alcoaensis*, this species must be considered in high risk of extinction, due to its limited range, despite the fact that the type locality is nowadays preserved as an archaeological site.

Belgrandia heussi C. R. Boettger, 1963 (Figs. 26-48, 75, 76)

Belgrandia heussi C. R. Boettger, 1963. *Arch. Moll.*, 92: 40. [Type locality: Lis River, which has its springs on the northern slope of Maciço Calcário Estremenho, and the mouth about 30 km south of the Mondego River, in the center of Portugal].

Type material: Holotype in SMF (167898).

Type locality: Rio Liz, Portugal.

Other material studied: Spring of the Anços River (NE3625), northern slope of Serra de Sicó, province of Beira Litoral, 210 sp, leg. A. de Oliveira, 3-April-2008 (MHNS: 100 sp; CAO: 110 sp). Springs of Abiul (NE3914), southern slope of Serra de Sicó, province of Beira Litoral, 20 sp, leg. S. Castelo and A. de Oliveira, 7-June-2008 (MHNS: 10 sp; CAO: 10 sp). Spring of the Lis River (ND1992), northern slope of Maciço Calcário Estremenho, province of Beira Litoral, 240 sp, leg. A. de Oliveira, 15-February-2008 (MHNS: 100 sp; CAO: 140 sp). Spring of Alcobertas (ND0864), southern slope of Maciço Calcário Estremenho, province of Ribatejo, about 320 sp, leg. S. Castelo and A. de Oliveira, 9-December-2007 (MHNS: 160 sp; CAO: 160 sp). Springs of the Alviela River (ND2466), southern slope of Maciço Calcário Estremenho, province of Ribatejo, 34 sp, leg. S. Castelo and A. de Oliveira, 8-December-2007 (MHNS: 30 sp; CAO: 4 sp). Olho de Mira (ND2376), in a depression valley, south of Mira de Aire, central Maciço Calcário Estremenho, province of Estremadura, 4 sp, leg. E. Rolán, 19-May-2003.

Description: Shell (Figs. 26-37) conical, somewhat elongated, whorls convex, with marked suture, fragile.

Protoconch (Figs. 39-45) with about one whorl, difficult to see because the separation with the teleoconch is not usually visible; diameter is variable in the above mentioned populations: nucleus between 100 and 150 μm ; first $\frac{1}{2}$ whorl between 200 and 260 μm . Microsculpture rough with minute depressions and irregular lines; in some shells from Lis (type locality) this sculpture is more attenuated (Figs. 44, 45).

Teleoconch with about three convex whorls with a deep suture, the spiral microsculpture scarcely appreciable and only visible under high magnification (Figs. 46, 47) and having slightly prosocline growth lines.

Aperture slightly and regularly ovoid, and a continuous and fine peristoma. Externally, there is an axial thickening slightly away from the end of the spire, which does not correspond with any internal depression into the aperture.

Dimensions between 1.5 and 1.9 mm in height.

Animal dark only on the dorsum of the head and between the eyes, with tentacles dark with a white line in the middle; the penis (Figs. 75, 76) is folded on its base and sharp at the extreme, presenting two small prominences one to each side and sometimes a black line in the middle; the sole of the foot is white.

The radula (Fig. 48) is typical of hydrobids, similar to that of the previ-

Figures 45-48. *Belgrandia heussi* C.R. Boettger, 1963. 45: microsculpture of the protoconch, shell from Lis; 46: microsculpture from a shell of Alcobertas; 47: microsculpture from a shell of Alviela; 48: radula, from a specimen of Alviela.

Figuras 45-48. Belgrandia heussi C.R. Boettger, 1963. 45: microescultura de la protoconcha, concha de Lis; 46: microescultura de una concha de Alcobertas; 47: microescultura de una concha de Alviela; 48: rádula, de un ejemplar de Alviela.

Figures 49-57. *Belgrandia alcoaensis* C.R. Boettger, 1963. 49-54: shells, 1,9, 1,7, 1,8, 1,7, 1,7 and 1,6 mm (MHNS); 55, 56: protoconchs; 57: microsculpture of the teleoconch.

Figuras 49-57. Belgrandia alcoaensis C.R. Boettger, 1963. 49-54: conchas, 1,9; 1,7; 1,8; 1,7; 1,7 y 1,6 mm (MHNS); 55, 56: protoconchas; 57: microescultura de la teleoconcha.

Figures 58-61. *Belgrandia alcoaensis* C. R. Boettger, 1963. 58: operculum; 59-61: radulae.
Figuras 58-61. *Belgrandia alcoaensis* C. R. Boettger, 1963. 58: opérculo; 59-61: rádulas.

ous species, with the cusps in the rachidian and lateral teeth a little shorter and less numerous.

Habitat: Under stones (limestone) lying on a coarse sandy bottom; always on surfaces devoid of all (macro) vegetation; in shady areas with running water. This species coexists with 5 other fresh-water gastropods: *Theodoxus* cf. *fluviatilis* (LINNAEUS, 1758)[Anços, Alcobertas, Alviela], *Potamopyrgus antipodarum* (GRAY J. E., 1843)[Abiul, Lis, Alcobertas, Alviela], *Radix balthica* (LINNAEUS, 1758)[Anços, Abiul], *Ancylus fluviatilis* (MÜLLER O. F., 1774) [Abiul, Lis, Alviela] and *Physella acuta* (DRAPARNAUD, 1805) [Abiul, Alviela].

Distribution: Contrarily to the other three Portuguese species, only known from the type locality, *Belgrandia heussi* is present in several springs dispersed in three provinces of central western Portugal: Beira Litoral (Anços, Abiul, Lis), Estremadura (Olho de Mira) and Ribatejo (Alcobertas, Alviela) (Fig. 78).

Belgrandia alcoaensis C. R. Boettger, 1963 (Figs. 49-61, 74)

Belgrandia heussi alcoaensis C. R. Boettger, 1963. *Arch. Moll.*, 92: 42. [Type locality: Alcoa River, which has its springs in the western slope of Maciço Calcário Estremenho, and after joining the Baça River, has its mouth about 35 km south of the Lis River, in the center of Portugal].

Type material: A paratype represented in HAASE (2000: fig. 3 H).

Type locality: Rio Alcoa, Portugal.

Other material studied: More than 1000 sp, leg. E. Rolán, 22-November-1991 (MHNS); 26 sp, leg. A. de Oliveira, 12-February-2008 (CAO). Both from the spring of the Alcoa River (ND0476), in the small village of Chiqueda de Cima, at 2 km east of Alcobça, western slope of Maciço Calcário Estremenho, province of Estremadura, Portugal.

Description: Shell (Figs. 49-54) conical, somewhat elongated, whorls flat or scarcely convex, with marked suture, fragile.

Protoconch (Figs. 55, 56) with a little less than one whorl, the separation with the teleoconch being usually visible; diameter about 300 µm; nucleus about 125 µm; first ½ whorl, about 250 µm. Spiral microsculpture with minute depressions.

Teleoconch with about three or three and a quarter whorls, with some irregular, very depressed and scarcely visible

Remarks: The material examined from several localities, is not entirely uniform, small differences existing between them. However, after the study of the morphology of the shells, protoconchs, and soft parts we could not find enough differences to consider them as different species.

Belgrandia lusitanica (Paladilhe, 1867) may be distinguished by its deeper suture and convex whorls; the peristome more undulating, the thickening of the external lip slightly stronger and close to the end of the spire; the suture is less marked on the last whorl. The penis has a smaller prominence on its right side; the radula shows a more marked cusp in the rachidian and internal border of the lateral teeth.

Belgrandia silviae spec. nov. is constantly larger, with deeper suture, the peristoma more undulating, the external prominence of the last whorl larger and not disposed axially, the growth lines curved and the aperture has a deep cave near the end of the spire.

spiral striae and slightly prosocline growth lines (Fig. 57).

Aperture slightly ovoid, with a small deviation of the border of the external lip in the place where the spiral cords ends; there is a continuous and narrow peristoma. Externally, it is not possible to see any thickening near the external border.

Dimensions between 1.6 and 1.9 mm in height.

Animal dark only on the dorsum of the head and between the eyes, with tentacles dark with a white line in the middle; the penis (Fig. 74) is folded on

Figures 62-68. *Belgrandia boscae* (Salvaña, 1887). 62-64: shells, 2.0, 1.9, 1.9 mm; 65: protoconch; 66, 67: microsculpture of the protoconch; 68: radula.

Figuras 62-68. Belgrandia boscae (Salvaña, 1887). 62-64: conchas, 2,0; 1,9 y 1,9 mm; 65: protoconcha; 66, 67: microescultura de la protoconcha; 68: rádula.

Figures 69-77. Soft parts and penis. 69: *Belgrandia lusitanica*, Quinta das Lágrimas; 70-73: *B. silviae* spec. nov., and several variations of the penis, Alcabideque; 74: *B. alcoensis*, Alcoa River; 75, 76: *B. heussi*, and variation of the penis, from the spring of Lis River; 77: *B. boscae*, Fuente de la Corroba, Tarragona.

Figuras 69-77. Partes blandas y penes. 69: *Belgrandia lusitanica*, Quinta das Lágrimas; 70-73: *B. silviae* spec. nov., con algunas variaciones del penis, Alcabideque; 74: *B. alcoensis*, Rio Alcoa; 75, 76: *B. heussi*, con variaciones del penis, del nacimiento del Río Lis; 77: *B. boscae*, Fuente de la Corroba, Tarragona.

its base and sharp at the extreme, presenting two small prominences one to each side and sometimes a black line in the middle; the sole of the foot is white.

Operculum (Fig. 58) ovoid, translucent, with the nucleus a little lateral.

The radula (Figs. 59-61) is typical of hydrobids, similar to that of the previous species although the cusps in the rachidian and lateral teeth are a little shorter and less numerous.

Habitat: Under stones (limestone) lying on a coarse sandy bottom; always on surfaces devoid of (macro) vegetation. This species coexists with 4 other freshwater gastropods: *Theodoxus* cf. *flu-*

viatilis (LINNAEUS, 1758), *Potamopyrgus antipodarum* (GRAY J.E., 1843), *Ancylus fluviatilis* (MÜLLER O.F., 1774) and *Physella acuta* (DRAPARNAUD, 1805).

Distribution: Known from the type locality only (Fig. 78).

Remarks: *Belgrandia alcoensis* was considered as a subspecies by Haase (2000: 185) after having only examined one shell (paratype). In the present work, we have examined many specimens and consider it very different from the other Portuguese species due to the almost flat whorls, especially the last one, the prominent spiral cord and the lack of any axial thickening.

Figure 78. UTM 100 km squares distribution map of *Belgrandia* in Spain.
 Figura 78. Mapa de distribución de *Belgrandia* en España. Cuadrículas UTM de 100 km de lado.

Belgrandia lusitanica, *Belgrandia heussi* and *Belgrandia silviae* spec. nov. may be distinguished by their deeper suture and more convex whorls, the last one not angulated, as well as the existence of a prominence or axial thickening on the external lip.

Like *Belgrandia lusitanica* and *Belgrandia silviae* spec. nov., this species must

be considered in high risk of extinction, due to its limited range. This risk was recently increased by human intervention on the bed of the Alcoa River, from near its spring down the stream to the center of the village of Chiqueda de Cima. In the course of the last sampling in the site (February-2008), only a few specimens were observed.

Table I. Schematic differences of the characters of the species of *Belgrandia* in Iberian Peninsula.
 Tabla I. Diferencias entre las especies de *Belgrandia* de la península ibérica.

	<i>B. lusitanica</i>	<i>B. heussi</i>	<i>B. alcoensis</i>	<i>B. silviae</i>	<i>B. boscae</i>
Geographic distribution	Middle Portugal	Middle Portugal	Middle Portugal	Middle Portugal	Eastern Spain
Spiral cord	Sometimes slightly	Not apreciable	Very evident	Very evident	Not apreciable
Last whorl with peripheral angulation	Not apreciable	Not apreciable	Very evident	Slightly evident	Not apreciable
Last whorl	Convex	Convex	Convex	Almost flat	Convex
Axial external lip thickening	Axially disposed	Axially disposed slight	Not apreciable	Very prominent in the middle	Axially disposed
Columella	Somewhat separated	Somewhat separated	Adherent	Adherent	Somewhat separated
Excavation in the aperture	No	No	No	Very important	No
Suture	Strangulating slightly last whorl	Not strangulating	Not strangulating	Strangulating slightly last whorl	Not strangulating
Peristome	weakly undulating	weakly undulating	weakly undulating	Strongly undulating	weakly undulating
Diameter of protoconch nucleus	90 µm	100-150 µm	125 µm	130 µm	130 µm
Diameter of protoconch half whorl	240 µm	200-260 µm	250 µm	260 µm	275 µm
Height of the shell	1,4-1,9 mm	1,5-1,9 mm	1,6-1,9 mm	1,7-2,1 mm	1,6-2,2 mm

Belgrandia boscae (Salvaña, 1887) (Figs. 62-68, 77)

Hydrobia boscae Salvaña, 1887. *Crón. Cient., Barcelona*, 10: 141. [Type locality: In the springs of Gandía, Valencia, Spain]

Type material: After BOETERS (1988) and HAASE (2000), untraceable.

Type locality: Springs at Gandía, Valencia.

Material examined: YK11. 100 sp, road from Valencia to Teruel, in Navajas (Castellón) in front of the hotel Navas Altas (29-September-1990)(MHNS). YK02. 50 sp, Benafer, in the river near Fuente de los Nogales (Castellón) (29-September-1990)(MHNS). YK11. 50 sp, road from Segorbe to Artana, in Castellnovo, near the river (30-September-1990). YK11. 100 sp, Segorbe (Castellón), Fuente de los 50 caños (6-October-1990)(MHNS). XJ77. about 100 sp, Road from Requena to Valencia, in Siete Aguas (Fuente del Retiro, at 2 Kms) (8-October-1990) (MHNS). BF91. About 100 sp, Tarragona, Fuente de la Torre de la Carroba (3-July-1991) (MHNS).

Description: Shell (Figs. 62-64) oval-cylindrical, somewhat elongated, whorls convex, with deep suture.

Protoconch (Fig. 65) with about 1 whorl, the separation with the teleoconch being very difficult to see; diameter: nucleus about 130 µm; first ½ whorl, about 275 µm. Microsculpture (Figs. 66, 67) with minute depressions, which

under high magnification (Fig. 67) are seen to present depressed cavities.

Teleoconch with about three whorls, with only prosocline growth lines.

Aperture slightly ovoid, continuous and with a fine peristoma, a little undulating and everted. The contact area with the previous whorl is small. Externally, a little before the end of the spire, there is

an axial elongated thickening, very constant, only absent from juveniles.

Dimensions between 1.6 and 2.2 mm in height.

Animal dark, with tentacles with some pigment on the borders; the dorsum of the head is dark, only light on spaces around the eyes and the anterior part of the snout; behind the eyes there is a triangular space with cream or cream-yellowish colour; the penis (Fig. 77) is elongated, sharp-pointed, with an angle near its base, a little black on its anterior part, and sometimes with a small appendix on its left side, not always appreciable. The sole of the foot is white.

The radula (Fig. 68) is typical of hydrobids, with a central tooth with about 10 cusps, the central one scarcely more prominent; lateral teeth similar, with about ten cusps; the marginal ones are different, one with nearly 30 small and elongated cusps, and the other spoon-like with only few cusps.

Habitat: Under leaves and stones in very pure water in shady places.

Distribution: This species was found in several locations in the provinces of

eastern Spain: Cuenca, Valencia, Castellón and Tarragona (see BOETERS, 1988).

Remarks: BOETERS (1988) presented this species under the name *Belgrandia* cf. *marginata* (Michaud, 1831) but indicating clear differences from the topotypes of the true *B. marginata*. Therefore he states that perhaps the name for them could be *Belgrandia boscae*. We use this name because besides the morphological differences a large distance separates these populations from those of *B. marginata*.

There are quite clear differences from the Portuguese species, such as (Table I):

-*Belgrandia lusitanica* is the most similar, but the protoconch is smaller.

-*Belgrandia silvoiae* has a very important prominence at the end of the spire and an excavation inside the aperture, and also a spiral cord;

-*Belgrandia heussi* has a suture which is not so deep, the thickening of the last whorl less evident.

-*Belgrandia alcoensis* usually lacks the thickening and has a well marked spiral cord.

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